

The list of simplest episodes

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«Hero/heroine brings down enemy, and then enemy rises» - this episode was partially observed in the essay «Literary Clichés and the Age of Revolution» (Serhii Yaremko, 2023), it manifests itself mainly in fictions when the damaged body of antagonist becomes regenerated.

The episode «Hero/heroine gets into danger and then is rescued by his/her friend» is clearly seen in the Battle of the Long Night (Benioff, Weiss & Sapochnik, 2019) when Sir Jorah Mormont rescues his Quinn; it explains how Servant 2 supports Order during the Servant 1's rebellion.

The simplest episode «Hero/heroine gets the help of a friend, and then enemy punishes the friend» can be seen in the action «Hero/heroine meets the hard shelling» («The Dark Valley» (Prochaska, 2014)); its meaning lies in the imprisonment of Second Servant after an unsuccessful attempt to stop First Servant when that person starts committing acts to illegally get the prolongation of his/her being in power in society.

The episode «A gymnast beats the opponent(s) in fight and then he/she is bitten" is shown when a well-trained fighter faces the single, much stronger opponent or a group of opponents who are ordinary people and tells us that Chaos has no perspective in the war that force wages against Order; the current episode is clearly shown in the trailer for the PC game «Assassin's Creed: Origins» (Digic Pictures, 2017).

The episode «The performer of the task does not succeed, and then the doubler does the task» is often shown when a soldier is hit during an attack and then the next soldier kills an enemy; it can be seen in the movie «My Way» (Je-gyu, 2011) - I mean the action «Hero/heroine meets the next wave of enemies» in the scene where a group of Japanese kamikazes lead the fight against Soviet tanks. This simplest episode obviously shows the success of Second Servant in keeping the code in mind.

«Someone shows a weakness, and then the weak is murdered» - this episode focuses on the First Servant's fear of losing power in society and the subsequent complete slide under the influence of Chaos, and manifests itself when a fugitive sees his/her foot (hair, clothes, etc.) caught on the obstacle (this action has already been discussed in the essay «Literary Clichés and the Age of Revolution» (Serhii Yaremko, 2023)), among other ways.

The episode «Enemy avoids punishment by cheating, and then enemy meets the punishment caused by that cheating» - it refers to the two antagonistic characters and can be seen in episode 2 of the German TV series «Generation War» (Kolditz & Kadelbach, 2013). First servant makes the rebellion with the help of chaos, and then chaos fills that person's mind - this is the meaning of the episode we are watching. It can be added that in the action «Enemy accidentally releases hero/heroine from custody» (as seen in the movie «Sherlock Holmes: a Game of Shadows» (Ritchie, 2011) - I mean the scene where the wall is breached by a shell) we see another manifestation of the current phenomenon.

«Hero/heroine meets the danger caused by enemy and then successfully avoids the danger» - the simplest episode showing how Order fights the Servant 1 rebellion, and often seen when protagonist dodges a hard blow during the fight (a wall is smashed, not the protagonist's head), runs while antagonist shoots, and so on. In this case, I recall how Captain Wolf Larsen and the schooner «Ghost» dodge a great typhoon in the novel «The Sea Wolf» (London, 2000).

The episode «Enemy holds hero/heroine captive, and then hero/heroine frees himself/herself» tells about how Servant 2 is overcoming the lure of illicit pleasures offered by Chaos during the Servant 1's rebellion; it can be seen in the action «Hero/heroine pulls the bullet (the arrow, the sword, etc.) from his/her own body» (a good example of this action can be found in the movie «Seraphim Falls» (Von Ancken, 2006)).

The episode «Enemy pushes hero/heroine away with a blow, and then hero/heroine damages the obstacle with his/her own body» (it is seen mainly in fictions, as in the movie «I, Robot» (Proyas, 2004)) is one of the variants of the episode «An armed enemy attacks the unarmed hero/heroine, and then hero/heroine strikes enemy with his/her own weapon», which is also partially used in «Literary Clichés and the Age of Revolution» (Serhii Yaremko, 2023).

Now, I would like to report on two episodes related to the action «Master puts the servants to the test» - they are both quite rare and show the development of society as a test of loyalty to Law, while at the same time most of the actions and episodes focus on overcoming the consequences of Servant 1's rebellion against Order (we see here the manifestation of dualism). The episode «An unfaithful servant tries to kill his/her master with a gun, and then meets the absence of bullets» was already shown in the film «Red Sun» (Young, 1971) and illustrates the process of illegal possession of power in society, which First Servant performs. Next, «Hero/heroine sees a lure and does not fall into the trap,» as it was shown in the film «Death Race» (Anderson, 2008) - the episode that focuses on complete loyalty to Law which Servant 2 shows.

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The list of episodes

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